

INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF FEMALE SEXUAL ORGANS

Mirzayeva Nafisa Jo'raboyevna

Sariosya in the name of Abu Ali Ibn Sina

Technical School of Public Health

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10469441>

Abstract. *Inflammatory diseases of female genital organs take the first place among gynecological diseases. There are three principles for the classification of diseases of inflammation of the female genital organs. Inflammatory diseases of the female genital organs and their treatment are described in detail in this article.*

Key words: *genitals, vulvitis, colpitis, endometritis, pelvioperitonitis.*

ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ЖЕНСКИХ ПОЛОВЫХ ОРГАНОВ

Аннотация. *Воспалительные заболевания женских половых органов занимают первое место среди гинекологических заболеваний. Существует три принципа классификации заболеваний воспалительных процессов женских половых органов. Воспалительные заболевания женских половых органов и их лечение подробно описаны в этой статье.*

Ключевые слова: *половые органы, вульвит, кольпит, эндометрит, пельвиоперитонит.*

Etiological factors are infectious, mechanical, thermal, chemical, thrombosis, hemorrhage, tissue necrosis. Spread of infection by lymphogenous way, hematogenous way, canalicular way. The clinical course is acute, semi-acute, chronic and relapsing. Groups of microbes that cause disease are septic inflammatory diseases, specific inflammatory diseases.

Inflammation of the external genital organs, inflammation of the internal genital organs depending on the location of the disease. Infection is transmitted by exogenous and endogenous means. The clinical course of the disease depends on the virulence of the causative agent and the characteristics of the body's defenses.

INFLAMMATION OF EXTERNAL SEXUAL ORGANS

vulvitis - mainly inflammation of the labia. A woman complains of pain and itching in the vaginal area. When examined, it can be seen that the tissues are reddened and swollen, purulent discharges are coming, and wounds can be found.

Treatment: wash and clean with 2% boric acid solution, chamomile tincture, apply synthomycin or streptocidal emulsion, or apply primochka, i.e. cover with a napkin soaked in the solution.

Bartholinitis - inflammation of large vestibular glands. The area of the labia majora is characterized by severe pain, swelling and infiltration. If the inflammation is purulent, the body temperature rises. In the acute stage, the patient is prescribed to lie down, put an ice pack on the affected gland area, antibiotics and sulfanilamide drugs.

Purulent inflammation is treated surgically. The purulent area is opened and swabs soaked in 10% hypertonic sodium chloride solution, then swabs smeared with Vishnevsky ointment are placed in the cavity. At the stage of absorption, physiotherapeutic treatment UVCh is used.

INFLAMMATION OF INTERNAL SEXUAL ORGANS

Colpitis is an inflammation of the vagina. Vaginal discharge, vaginal itching and pain. When examined, it is seen that the vaginal wall is reddened, swollen, sometimes with light red small rashes and pus bubbles. In trichomonad colpitis, secretions are yellow-green foam, in fungal colpitis, in the form of a white mass. It is treated taking into account the causative agent of the disease. Vulvovaginitis is more common in girls. The reason is that it appears when foreign objects get into the vagina. Treatment depends on the etiological factor.

endocervicitis - inflammation of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal. Clinic. Light-headedness, pulling pains in the buttock region, as if lying down. When examined with the help of vaginal mirrors, it is found that the cervical canal is red, and purulent discharge is coming from the cervical canal.

The cure. Medicines with antibiotics, sulfanilamide. Rinsing the vagina and putting on tampons. Protorgol or Lugol solution is injected into the cervical canal.

Erosion of the cervix - damage, ulceration of the multilayered flat epithelium around the external opening of the cervix. The defect of the multi-layered flat epithelia of the vaginal part of the cervix is called true erosion. Affected by pathological secretions from the cervical canal, erosion occurs.

Chin erosion is light red in color, irregular in shape, and bleeds when touched. Cylindrical epithelia grow on the damaged area of the defect of the epithelia of the vaginal part of the uterus, and the wound appears to be healing. In fact, this situation is not recovery - it is a false (pseudo) erosion situation. Cylindrical epithelia act in the eroded area, blocking the path of the secretory glands, and small bubbles appear in the place where the secretion accumulates, which are called Nabotov's ovules (ovuli Nabotici). In pseudo-erosion, it is filled with cylindrical epithelium, and the surface of the erosion appears pale red.

Erosions are also formed when the mucous membrane in the torn areas of the cervical canal turns over (erosion ectropion).

9-rasm.

a - a healthy appearance of the cervix; b, d, e, f, g - different forms of cervical erosion.

Treatment: Medicinal baths, antimicrobial drugs, tampons are applied. Electrocoagulation after biopsy. Cryotherapy. Laser treatment is a new method.

endometritis - inflammation of the lining of the uterus. The clinic is throbbing pain in the lower abdomen and buttocks. An increase in body temperature, tachycardia, and muscle cramps are noticeable in the acute form. During bimanual examination, it is observed that the uterus is painful, partially enlarged, and purulent discharge is coming from the uterus.

salpingo-oophoritis – (adnexitis) inflammation of the uterus. If the inflammatory processes intensify, a purulent cyst - tuboovarian tumor (pyo - sactosalpinx) appears in the area of the uterus.

Inflammation of the uterus leads to childlessness, ectopic pregnancy, menstrual dysfunction. parametritis - inflammation of the uterine lining. Pain in the lower abdomen, legs and buttocks, difficulty urinating and going to the toilet due to severe pain, deterioration of the general condition, increase in body temperature are observed. A parametrial infiltrate can rupture into the bladder or rectum when suppurating.

pelvioperitonitis - inflammation of the peritoneum in the small pelvis, severe pain in the lower abdomen. The general condition of the patient worsens, the body temperature rises. Vomiting, constipation and flatulence are observed. Symptoms of intoxication: characterized by an acceleration of the pulse, a decrease in arterial pressure, dryness of the mouth, weakness.

peritonitis is a diffuse inflammation of the peritoneum, which occurs as a result of exacerbation of purulent pelvioperitonitis or rupture of purulent areas of the uterus. In this case, the intoxication is characterized by the fact that the body temperature rises to a high level, and the symptoms characteristic of the peritoneum are felt in all parts of the abdomen. It is treated operatively.

TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE SEXUAL ORGANS

It is recommended to use drugs that increase general strength, drugs that reduce the uterus, antibacterial therapy, sulfanilamide drugs, detoxification therapy, desensitizing therapy, symptomatic treatment, local treatment, and physiotherapeutic treatment. In the acute period of the disease, bed rest, rest, an ice pack is placed on the lower part of the abdomen.

Prevention of inflammatory diseases of female genital organs: during menstruation, childbirth, after abortion, following the rules of personal hygiene. Practice sexual hygiene. Prevention of abortions. Elimination of foci of all chronic diseases in the body.

REFERENCES

1. Ya.N. Allayarov. Reproductive health and contraceptive technology. - T.: "Istiqlo'l" publishing house, 2005.
2. Ya.N. Allayarov, M.I. Rasulova, D.U. Yusupova. Pathological obstetrics. - Samarkand, 2007.
3. Ya.N. Allayarov. Obstetrics. - T.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2008.
4. Ya.N. Allayarov, N. I. Zokirova, A. T. Safarov, F. Q. Askarova. Emergency help in obstetrics. - Samarkand, 2009.
5. R.U. Arziklov. Basics of Reproductive Health. - T.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2010.

6. Yu.A. Gurkin, V.I. Gritsyuk. Gynecology. Directory of the obstetrician-gynecologist. Moscow - St. Petersburg, 2005.
7. M.F. Ziyayeva, G.Kh. Mavlyanova. Gynecology. - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 2007.